

Integrative Analysis of Physiological, Epigenomic, and Transcriptomic Changes in *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* Exposed to Ciprofloxacin and Cadmium

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Experimental design

Cultures of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* were exposed for 96 h to a concentration range of **ciprofloxacin** (0.114, 0.202, 0.533 mg L⁻¹) and **cadmium** (0.099, 0.293, 1.856 mg L⁻¹) under controlled laboratory conditions. Physiological responses were measured across all concentrations, while global DNA methylation and transcriptomic analyses were performed at EC20 exposure levels to assess molecular and epigenetic stress responses.

No significant methylated genes found

No significant differentially methylated genes were detected following exposure of *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* to neither **ciprofloxacin** nor **cadmium**.

Conclusion

Phaeodactylum tricornutum shows strong physiological and transcriptomic responses to Cadmium, indicating pronounced stress and metabolic reprogramming. In contrast, Ciprofloxacin induces minimal molecular changes, and no gene-level DNA methylation differences are detected under either exposure.

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